

Synthesis of *O*-Dimethylreticulol and (\pm)5-Methylmellein

J. N. CHATTERJEA, B. K. BANERJEE, C. BHAKTA & J. MUKERJI

Department of Chemistry, University of Patna, Patna

Received 12 December 1971

O-Dimethylreticulol and (\pm)5-methylmellein have been synthesised.

A metabolic isocoumarin reticulol, m.p. 193°–93.5° has been isolated from *Streptomyces rubrireticuli* by Mitscher *et al.*¹ and structure (I) has been proposed on the basis of chemical transformation and spectral data. Similarly (–)5-methylmellein (VII; R = H) was isolated from the main phytotoxic metabolite of *Fusicoccum amygdali* fusicoccein A by A. Ballio *et al.*⁴ It has been assigned the structure (VII, R = H) on the basis of the degradative works and spectral properties.

The present communication deals with the synthesis² of *O*-dimethylreticulol and (\pm)5-methylmellein. Thus 5,6,7-trimethoxyindan-1-one prepared from trimethylgallic acid according to the literature³ afforded 2-nitroso derivative on treatment with methyl nitrite and hydrochloric acid. Beckmann transformation followed by hydrolysis furnished 3,4,5-trimethoxyhomophthalic acid (IV) in fairly good yield. The dimethyl ester (V) prepared by the action of ethereal diazomethane in the usual manner was hydrolysed with methanolic caustic potash yielding 2-methoxycarbonyl-3,4,5-trimethoxyphenylacetic acid (VI). The derived acid chloride on treatment with diethyl ethoxymagnesiummalonate and subsequent hydrolysis with acids gave 6,7-dimethoxy-8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (II) (violet ferric reaction). The compound (II) on methylation with methyl iodide and potassium carbonate in acetone solution gave (III) which was found to be identical in all respects with the methylated product of the natural specimen of reticulol (I) kindly supplied by Dr. E. Petterson.

The synthesis of (\pm)5-methylmellein was similarly carried out from 4-methyl-7-methoxyindan-1-one⁵ which gave the 2-nitroso derivative with methyl nitrite and then converted into 3-methoxy-6-methylhomophthalic acid (VIII). The derived methyl ester (IX) when partially hydrolysed with methanolic caustic potash yielded 2-methoxy-carbonyl-3-methoxy-6-methylphenylacetic acid (X). The acid chloride of (X) was similarly converted into 3,5-dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (blue ferric reaction). This on hydrogenation with palladised charcoal in acetic acid furnished (\pm)5-methylmellein (VII, R = H) characterised by the *o*-methyl ether (VII, R = CH₃) (negative ferric reaction).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Nitroso-5,6,7-trimethoxyindan-1-one : 5,6,7-Trimethoxyindan-1-one³ (8 g.) was dissolved in minimum volume of methyl alcohol containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (12 ml.) and methyl nitrite gas was passed into it till the solution was saturated. On cooling, the nitroso derivative (8 g.) separated as needles, m.p. 198°–200°. On recrystallisation from acetic acid it was obtained as pale yellow shining needles, m.p. 201°–2° (decomp.). (Found : N, 5.35; C₁₂H₁₃O₅N requires : N, 5.58%).

3,4,5-Trimethoxyhomophthalic Acid : The above nitroso compound (7.5 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (30 ml; 10%) and treated with *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride (7.5 g.) at 50° with shaking. On raising the temperature to 80°, the suspended matter went into solution. It was cooled and filtered. The solution was refluxed with more of sodium hydroxide (30 ml; 10%) for 10 hr. On acidification 3,4,5-trimethoxyhomophthalic acid separated as an oil which on cooling in ice bath slowly solidified (4 g.). It was crystallised from chloroform as tiny prisms, m.p. 141°–42° (Found : C, 53.0; H, 4.9. C₁₂H₁₄O₇ requires : C, 53.3; H, 5.1%).

Dimethyl 3,4,5-trimethoxyhomophthalate : The foregoing homophthalic acid (3.8 g.) was esterified with ethereal diazomethane (from 12 g. of nitrosomethyl urea). The ester (3.3 g.) distilled at 180°/0.5 mm. as a colourless thick oil. (Found : C, 56.0; H, 5.9. C₁₄H₁₈O₇ requires : C, 56.3; H, 6.0%).

2-Methoxycarbonyl-3,4,5-trimethoxyphenylacetic Acid : Dimethyl 3,4,5-trimethoxyhomophthalate (1 g.) was refluxed with methanolic caustic potash (1.88 ml.; 10%) for 20 min. After the removal of methanol under reduced pressure, the solution was cooled, diluted and acidified when 2-methoxycarbonyl-3,4,5-trimethoxyphenylacetic acid separated as solid. On crystallisation from benzene it was obtained as colourless tiny needles, m.p. 148°–50°; yield 0.9 g. (Found : C, 54.6; H, 5.6. C₁₃H₁₆O₇ requires : C, 54.9; H, 5.7%). ν_{max} 1735 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl) and 1695 cm⁻¹ (carboxyl).

6,7-Dimethoxy-8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin : A solution of 2-methoxycarbonyl-3,4,5-trimethoxyphenylacetic acid (0.8 g.) in dry benzene (1 ml) was treated with oxalyl chloride (1 ml.) at 10° for one and half hours and then kept at room temp. for 4 hr. The excess of oxalyl chloride was then removed under reduced pressure and the last traces removed by two successive additions of dry benzene followed by its removal under reduced pressure. The resultant *acid chloride* was obtained as a thick brown oil.

Diethyl ethoxymagnesiummalonate was then prepared by heating with exclusion of moisture a mixture of clean magnesium (0.32 g.), dry alcohol (0.3 ml.) and carbon tetrachloride (0.08 ml). When the reaction started, a mixture of alcohol (1.28 ml), dry ether (30 ml.) and diethyl malonate (2 ml.) was added carefully with shaking. The mixture was refluxed for 3 hr when all the magnesium nearly dissolved and the freshly prepared acid chloride of 2-methoxycarbonyl-3,4,5-trimethoxyphenylacetic acid in ether (20 ml.) was added with continued stirring and the mixture refluxed for 2 hr when the magnesium complex separated as yellow coloured jelly. On working up in the usual manner, the residual brown oil was boiled with a mixture of acetic acid (5 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (2.5 ml) for 4 hr. The solution after concentration in vacuum was treated with ice water and extracted with ether, washed first with sodium bicarbonate solution and then water and dried (MgSO_4). On evaporation of the solvent, 6,7-dimethoxy-8-hydroxy-3-methyl isocoumarin separated as cream coloured solid (0.4 g.). It crystallised from benzene in dull yellow needles, m.p. 193°–94°. (Found : C, 61.0; H, 5.2. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 61.0; H, 5.1%). ν_{\max} 1680 cm^{-1} (chelated carbonyl) and 3425 cm^{-1} (phenolic hydroxyl).

O-Dimethylreticulol : 6,7-Dimethoxy-8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (0.1 g.) was refluxed with methyl iodide (1 ml) and potassium carbonate (1 g.) in acetone (5 ml) for 20 hr. On working up in the usual manner, *O*-dimethylreticulol appeared from alcohol as colourless plates, m.p. and mixed m.p. 190° with the authentic sample prepared in a similar way from the natural reticulol obtained through the courtesy of Dr. E. Petterson. The I.R. of the two products were also superimposable. (Found : C, 62.3; H, 5.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 62.4; H, 5.6%).

2-Nitroso-4-methyl-7-methoxyindan-1-one : A solution of 4-methyl-7-methoxyindan-1-one (14 g.) prepared according to the literature⁵ was dissolved in minimum volume of methyl alcohol. To this cooled solution concentrated hydrochloric acid (22 ml) was added slowly when the solution developed a dark brown colour. The solution was then saturated with methyl nitrite gas at room temp. On cooling the nitroso compound (14.5 g.) separated in crystalline form. On recrystallisation from acetic acid, it separated as yellow needles, m.p. 244°–45° (decomp.) (Found : C, 64.8; H, 5.7. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires ; C, 64.4; H, 5.3%).

3-Methoxy-6-methylhomophthalic Acid : A solution of the above nitroso compound (14 g.) in sodium hydroxide (60 ml; 10%) was gradually treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (14 g.) with occasional shaking at 50° and the reaction was completed by heating for one and half hours at 80°. The solution was cooled, filtered and refluxed with a further quantity of sodium hydroxide (70 ml; 10%) for 10 hr. The solution was cooled, filtered and acidified when 3-methoxy-6-methylhomophthalic acid (5 g.) separated as an oil which on cooling slowly solidified into cream coloured mass. On crystallisation from chloroform it separated as fine crystals, m.p. 169°–70°. (Found : C, 58.8; H, 5.5. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 58.9; H, 5.3%).

Dimethyl 3-methoxy-6-methylhomophthalate : The above homophthalic acid (4 g.) was esterified by treating with an ethereal solution of diazomethane (from 12 g. of nitrosomethylurea) in cold. The ester distilled at 175°–80°/0.1 mm. as colourless viscous oil. (Found : C, 61.7; H, 6.4. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 61.9; H, 6.3%).

2-Methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxy-6-methylphenylacetic Acid : The dimethyl ester (1.2 g.) was refluxed with methanolic potassium hydroxide (2.8 ml; 10%) for 20 min. The methanol was removed under reduced pressure, water added and acidified with 5 *N* hydrochloric acid when *2-methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxy-6-methylphenylacetic acid* separated as fine crystals. On recrystallisation from benzene it was obtained as colourless silky needles, (yield 1 g), m.p. 108°–9°. (Found : C, 60.4; H, 6.2. $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ requires : C, 60.5; H, 5.9%). ν_{max} 1730 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl) and at 1695 cm^{-1} (carboxyl).

3,5-Dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin : The foregoing half ester (0.9 g.) dissolved in dry benzene (1 ml.) was treated with oxalyl chloride (1 ml) at room temp. for 4 hr. The excess of oxalyl chloride was removed in vacuum when the *2-methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxy-6-methylphenylacetyl chloride* was obtained as a dark brown oil.

Diethyl ethoxymagnesiummalonate was then prepared by adding carbon tetrachloride (0.03 ml) and dry ethanol (0.16 ml) to clean magnesium (0.17 g.). It was heated to 70° and to it a mixture of diethylmalonate (1 ml), dry ether (15 ml) and ethyl alcohol (0.64 ml) added dropwise. It was then refluxed for 3 hr when nearly all the magnesium dissolved. To the cooled solution, *2-methoxycarbonyl-3-methoxy-6-methylphenylacetyl chloride* dissolved in dry ether (10 ml) was added and refluxed gently for 2 hr when the magnesium complex separated as jelly. On working up in the usual manner, the residual oil was heated with a mixture of acetic acid (5 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 ml) for 4 hr. It was cooled and concentrated under reduced pressure. It was then extracted with ether, washed first with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and then water and dried ($MgSO_4$). On evaporation of the solvent, *3,5-dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin* separated as straw coloured solid. On crystallisation from benzene, it was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 150°–51°. (Found : C, 69.5; H, 6.6. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires : C, 69.5; H, 5.4%). ν_{max} 1680 cm^{-1} (chelated carbonyl). It is soluble in sodium hydroxide (1%) and developed blue ferric reaction.

(±)*5-Methylmellein* : The *3,5-dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin* (0.2 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (1 ml.) and hydrogenated in presence of palladised charcoal (0.05 g.; 10%) till no more of hydrogen was absorbed. The solution was filtered and on concentration afforded (±)*5-methylmellein* in colourless needles. On recrystallisation from benzene it was obtained as fine needles, m.p. 140°–41°. (Found : C, 68.5; H, 6.4. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3$ requires : C, 68.8; H, 6.2%). ν_{max} 1725 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl). It developed bluish-violet ferric reaction.

(±)*O-Methyl-5-methylmellein* : (±)*5-Methylmellein* (0.1 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone (3 ml) and refluxed with methyl iodide (1 ml) and potassium carbonate (1 g.) for 20 hr. On working up in the usual manner, *O-methyl-5-methylmellein* was obtained as colourless crystals. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol it separated as plates, m.p. 139°–40°. (Found : C, 70.0; H, 6.4. $C_{12}H_{13}O_3$ requires : C, 70.2; H, 6.3%).

Two of us (C.B. & J.M.) wish to thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for the provision of junior fellowships.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. L. A. Mitscher, W. W. Andres and W. McCrae, *Experientia*, 1964, **20**(5), 258.
2. J. N. Chatterjea, J. Mukerji, C. Bhakta and B. K. Banerjee, *Current Sci.*, 1969, **38**(20), 493; *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, **72**, 299.
3. J. Koo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 720, 1890.
4. A. Ballio, S. Barcellona and B. Santurbano, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, **31**, 3723.
5. K. Auwers, *Chem. Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 3692.

